

LINGUISTICS OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ITS STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS

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Abstract: the article includes that language stands out among other phenomena of reality. Some branches of linguistics are listed.

Key words: linguistics, English, student, teacher, higher educational institution.

In learning any language, it is important to pay attention to a number of its components. This also applies to linguistics. The term linguistics comes from the Latin word "lingua", which means "language". Therefore, linguistics is the science that studies language. It provides information about how language stands out among other phenomena of reality, what are its elements and units, how and what changes occur in the language. Linguistics of the English language explores the structures and patterns of a given language, its functioning and development, and also compares it with other languages to identify links with it. Linguistics is the study of language, which explores its structures and patterns, functioning and development, and also compares different languages in order to identify links between them. The word "linguistics" is borrowed. If you stick to the version of Russian origin, then it sounds like "linguistics". Linguistics is general and particular. General linguistics - examines, examines and compares all the languages of the world as a whole. Private linguistics considers only one specific language. In our case, English. Linguistics is subdivided into scientific linguistics and practical linguistics. Most often, linguistics refers to scientific linguistics. Linguistics is part of semiotics as a science of signs. Hence, linguistics is a generalization of all sciences about language. Phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, stylistics and others are its branches. It is impossible to list everything that linguistics includes. Some sciences are so closely intertwined with each other that their differences are blurred, they can be children of several other sciences at the same time.

Speaking of grammar, for example, we can clearly say that it has two subsections: morphology and syntax, which, in turn, have their own branches. All of them are parts of linguistics. The language is not given to the linguist in direct observation, only the facts of speech or linguistic phenomena are directly observed, that is, the speech acts of native speakers of a living language together with their texts or linguistic material.

Linguistics involves observation; registration and description of the facts of speech; putting forward hypotheses to explain these facts; formulation of hypotheses in the form of theories and models describing the language; their

experimental verification and refutation; prediction of speech behavior. The explanation of facts can be internal through linguistic facts, or external through physiological, psychological, logical or social facts.

Empirical linguistics extracts linguistic data in two ways. First: the method of experiment - observation of the behavior of speakers of living dialects. The second way: operating with philological methods, collecting materials from written languages and interacting with philology, which studies written monuments in their cultural and historical ties.

Theoretical linguistics studies linguistic laws and formulates them in the form of theories. It can be either descriptive (describing real speech) or normative (indicating how “should” be spoken and written).

- Phonology. The study of speech structure within a language, including both the patterns of basic speech units and the accepted rules of pronunciation, is known as phonology.ii The smallest units of sound that make up a language are called phonemes. For example, the word “that” contains three phonemes the “th” represents one phoneme /th/, the “a” maps to the short a sound /ă/, and the “t” to its basic sound /t/.

- Morphology. Moving to the next level of language, we find the study of the smallest units of meaning, morphemes. Morphemes include base words, such as “hat,” “dog,” or “love,” as well as affixes, such as “un-,” “re-,” the plural “s” or “es,” and the past tense “ed.” Knowledge of the morphology of our language is critical to vocabulary development and reflects the smallest building blocks for comprehension.

- Syntax. The study of how individual words and their most basic meaningful units are combined to create sentences is known as syntax. As words are grouped together when we communicate, we must follow the rules of grammar for our language, in other words, its syntax. It is the knowledge of syntax that allows us to recognize that the following two sentences, while containing different word order and levels of complexity, have the same meaning.

In English language instruction, the main thing that should be considered is English linguistics components. As it is the application of the linguistic knowledge, the English language instruction will be well designed based on such components. Linguistics has the purpose to explore the general principles on which a language is constructed and operate as system of communication. The achievements of linguistic inquiry are implemented in effective language teaching. On the three views of seeing the language, the implementation of these views in English teaching mostly depends on the purpose of language instruction.

The language studied by the linguist is the language-object, and the language in which the theory is formulated is the metalanguage. The metalanguage of linguistics has its own specifics: it includes linguistic terms, names of languages and language groups, systems of special writing (transcription and transliteration).

Metatexts are created in a metalanguage - these are grammars, dictionaries, linguistic atlases, maps of the geographical distribution of languages, language textbooks, phrasebooks, etc. It is possible to speak not only about languages, but also about language in general, since the languages of the world have much in common [1, p. 37]. Private linguistics studies a single language, a group of related languages, or a pair of contacting languages. The study of the common features of all languages empirically and deductively, the general laws of the functioning of the language, the development of methods for the study of the language is carried out by general linguistics. Its part is a typology that compares different languages regardless of the degree of their relationship and draws conclusions about the language in general. Monolingual linguistics is limited to the description of one language, but it can single out different linguistic subsystems within it and study the relationships between them. Diachronic linguistics compares different time slices in the history of a language. External linguistics describes the language in all its variety of social variants and functions. Internal linguistics considers language as a homogeneous code, where the description can be oriented towards written and oral speech; may be limited only to the "correct" language or take into account various deviations from it; can only describe a system of patterns that operate in all varieties of a language or include rules for choosing between options depending on extralinguistic factors. So linguistics is the science of language.

References:

1. Mikhailov M.M. Bilingualism: problems, searches. Cheboksary, 1989. 160 p.
2. Evdokimov, M.S. Handbook of American-British Correspondences / M.S. Evdokimov, G.M. Shleev. - Flint, 2001. - 251 p.
3. Chernov, G.V. American version. English-Russian/Russian-English Dictionary/ GV Chernov. - M., 2001. - 1062 p.
4. Cambridge dictionary [Electr. resource]. - Access mode: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/en/> - Access date: 01/10/2019.